

EFFECTIVE LEARNING OF SCIENCE THROUGH DIGITAL STRATEGIES FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT IN EKITI STATE UNIVERSITY ADO EKITI, NIGERIA

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Abstract

The study examined effective teaching and learning of science through digital strategies for sustainable development in Ekiti state University, Nigeria. The research design adopted for this study was a mixed method involving quasi-experimental and descriptive survey. The sample was 300 intact science students. Data were collected from two sources, quasi experimental and Control groups and questionnaire. To ascertain the face and content validity of the instruments, experts in the fields of Information Technology and Test, Measurement and Evaluation were given the package and copies of the questionnaire to ascertain the validity. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation while t-test and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed that there was significant relationship between availability of digital strategies and students' academic performance in science. The findings showed that the difference in mean performance scores of students exposed to digital strategies and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Post-test stage was high and improvement in their academic performance was evident as against the pre-test. The study revealed some level of students' digital literacy which invariably would enable them contribute to sustainable development of the university and the nation at large. It was therefore concluded that digital strategies are effective tools to enhance performance and develop skills for sustainability. It was therefore recommended that there should provision of more digital facilities and trainings for lecturers through workshops/ seminars.

Keywords: Teaching, Learning, Digital Strategies, Students.

INTRODUCTION

Ekiti State University is a citadel of knowledge where intellectuals are raised and brought up to be agents of remarkable change. She serves as a hub of research and knowledge production with the ability to contribute to national sustainable development. This affirms importance of well-trained, 21st-century pedagogically informed and digitally literate teachers in impacting knowledge to her students, the future leaders of tomorrow. Ekiti State University (EKSU) founded in 1982, has made great stride in adopting digital devices in teaching and learning process hence today she is rated as the best State University in Nigeria and the 12th among Federal and State universities.

The lockdown of 2020 as a result of the outbreak of COVID 19 pandemic opened the door for integrating digital strategies in teaching and learning process. EKSU is gradually leveraging digital strategies to improve teaching and learning especially in science education and aligning it with global sustainability. Some of the digital strategies adopted at this time included virtual

platforms. Other progress made included students' online registration, online payment of fees, course enrolment, result checking and digitalization of admission processes. Staff and students were trained to create digital awareness on the use of digital tools to encourage lecturers to adopt digital presentation methods like email, e-note and PowerPoint. There were also departmental digital trainings on capacity building seminars. Multimedia projectors and smart boards were installed in some designated lecture halls. Computer laboratories, especially in the faculties, were updated and expanded with Internet wi-fi connectivity. There was e-assessment, submission of assignments, students' records digitalized in every department and transcript processing automated. The implication is that the contributions of higher institutions in the creation and dissemination of useful knowledge as well as in collaborating with society on the application of such knowledge (Akinyemi et al, 2022) cannot be overemphasized. However, it is not so certain all lecturers deploy digital strategies in instructional delivery for students' skills acquisition to enable them contribute to sustainable development.

Quality education remains the objective of the Nigerian education system to promote long-term national sustainable development, No nation can develop without quality teachers because they play a critical role in achieving quality education in any country of the world (United Nations, 2015). This requires change in pedagogy and method of instructional delivery. (Mynbayeva, Sadvakassova & Akshalova, (2018) stated that there should be considerable changes in the present pedagogy and revert to 21st-century pedagogies which rely on the efficacy and efficiency offered through Information and Communication Technology (ICT) tools such as smartphones and digital technologies in education. Many modern methods, such as problem-solving, flipped classroom, project-based learning, critical thinking, gamification, design thinking and competency-based learning approaches have resulted in significant changes in 21st-century pedagogies which has invariably influenced the way teaching and learning process is carried out globally. Following the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, several institutions like Ekiti State University adopted virtual learning via various online platforms to ensure the continuity of academic activities. Among the various technological advancements tools and platforms that allow seamless integration of ICT tools and other digital technology adopted, are Google classroom, what's App, Flipped classroom, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and other online platforms. These impactful technological innovations have the potential to revolutionize educational practices (Chetry, 2024, Ogunsola et al., 2021, Zheng, 2022). The use of these innovative technologies has helped in closing the communication gap between students and teachers and digital skills to function effectively in the 21st century workforce hence the suggestion for digital approach to teaching and learning process. Digital strategies are intentional use of digital tools like educational games and interactive modules to enhance students' engagement, to improve retention of scientific concepts related to sustainable development and pedagogies to promote learning activities. The strategies are comprehensive plan to integrate technological tools, platforms and e-resources to improve learning outcomes and also to create engaging learning experiences.

Digital strategies improve teaching methods by making science learning more engaging, practical, and accessible. Through interactive simulations, 3D models, and virtual experiments, complex scientific concepts in physics, chemistry, biology and engineering can be simplified.

These tools promote deeper understanding, critical thinking and problem-solving skills among students. Institutions of Higher learning ensure the availability of a workforce capable of driving national development through the production of graduates who are better equipped with scientific knowledge and digital competence. These digital strategies foster innovation and personalized experiences to build a skilled workforce and promote sustainability. They empower students with the knowledge and skills necessary to address environmental issues to contribute to its achievement of sustainable development goals.

Digital strategies range from e-learning platforms to immersive technologies and flipped learning among others. Flipped learning involves video lectures and other learner support materials designed to teach and guide students outside of the classroom. This allows profitable class time to be used on more engaging and collaborative activities. According to Taylor, Fudge, Mirriahi & Maarten de Laat (2021), flipped learning has a positive effect on students' engagement, the ability to self-pace learning, the provision of instant discussion and feedback during class time. Therefore, lecturers are required to have a repertoire of strategies that would allow them to maintain control over their learning environment. Digital strategies can transform how complex concepts in science are communicated, provide access to global knowledge and enable experiential learning through simulations and virtual experiments (Tondeur et al., 2017). Science is pivotal for sustainable development in the 21st century. It is a key component of education for sustainable development that aims at equipping individuals with knowledge, skills and value needed to create a sustainable future. The role of science in sustainable development is cardinal. Biology for instance permeates all the science-related courses including Biochemistry, Medicine, Pharmacy and Nursing. As a result of this, Biology is a prerequisite to other professions like medicine, agriculture, dentistry and many others due to the critical position it occupies among the natural sciences. Science builds a workforce that is capable of driving sustainable development initiatives to equip individuals with technical expertise needed to design, implement and manage sustainable projects. It also enhances understanding of the natural world and impact human activities on the environment. Science for Sustainable Development (SSD) focuses on equipping students with scientific knowledge and skills to address global challenges. Hence the clarion cry for innovative method of instructional delivery in order to change the statu quo.

Technology-supported instruction empowers lecturers to shift from traditional didactic method of instructional delivery to more learner-centred approach. This paradigm shift has shown to positively enhanced students' learning outcomes. Nigerian universities where lecturer-to-student ratio is often high, technology serves as a bridge to personalize learning, enabling educators to design adaptive content that meets learners at their own point of learning needs (Salman et al., 2021). Teaching with technology makes learning process more flexible, active and goal-directed. It also motivates students to learn and caters for their individual learning styles.

Several studies have revealed that despite the relative importance and popularity of science and its prominence in everyday lives and sustainable development, students' performance has not been encouraging. Students have not been able to acquire knowledge transfer to real life

situation especially in workforce. Researches attributed this poor academic performance to the problem of large class sizes, poor methods of teaching, poor digital literacy and insufficient technology facilities. Hence there is a clarion call from all every fabric of the society concerning graduates not being able to fit into today workforce due to lack of sufficient and relevant skills to function well and contribute to national sustainable development. Akinyemi et al (2022), corroborated this assertion in his remark that ‘there has been growing concerned about what students learn and also how they learn it’. One way of proferring solution to these problems is believed to be through employment of digital strategies approach in instructional delivery. Digital strategies allow lecturers to deliver content in various forms through multimedia approach and blended learning. Jian-hua and Hong (2012) opined that application of multimedia technology can help students learn vividly, clearly and realistically in the classroom. Blended learning is an effective way of interacting with students and online environment. It combines face- to -face teaching styles with online learning activities. According to Onajite (2025), blended learning brings together the sustenance of classroom educators while giving learners the privilege of discovering skills that are vital for sustainable development. Problem based learning activities is an example of blended learning using diverse digital learning resources that assist students to be self-confident and self-dependent which are necessary ingredients for the attainment of sustainable development. Hence the study examined effective learning of science through digital strategies for sustainable development in Ekiti state University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria.

Nigeria, like most developing countries, not wanting to be left behind in the use of technological innovations, has realised the importance of ICT in its development agenda. Nigerian government formulated policies to support integration of technology into teaching and learning process. For instance, the National Policy on Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education was promulgated to promote the use of ICT to improve teaching and learning across all levels of Education. The policy outlined various strategies for developing technology infrastructure, training educators and integrating it into the curriculum (Federal Ministry of Education, 2019).

Owoeye & Oso (2024) state that Nigerian Research and Education Network (NgREN) provided high speed internet connectivity to universities to foster access to global educational resources and collaborative research. It also provided network services and application like software, e-content, video conferencing and also promote innovative ways of teaching and learning. In 2020, it was reported that Covenant University invested much on creating a technology-driven environment deploying smart classrooms equipped with interactive boards and high-speed internet as well as digital libraries for learning and research. Obafemi Awolowo University also introduced e-learning platform to support online courses and to provide students with access to course materials, assignment, discussion to enhance lifelong learning.

The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2019 caused a global disruption to educational systems, leading to an abrupt shift from traditional face-to-face instruction to online learning. Ekiti State University, like many institutions, transitioned to digital platforms to continue academic activities during the lockdown. This shift significantly affected how lecturers

delivered instruction and exposed the limitations of conventional teaching methods in meeting the needs of 21st-century learners. Although the university has since upgraded its digital infrastructure to align with smart education trends, challenges remain in ensuring that students, particularly those in science disciplines, are adequately prepared for national development and equipped with relevant digital skills for today's workforce. The conventional mode of instruction is now seen as outdated in the face of rapid digitalisation, revealing a critical gap in science education for sustainable development. This study, therefore, investigates the effectiveness of teaching and learning science using digital strategies at Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti. It seeks to determine whether the use of digital tools enhances students' academic performance and fosters the development of digital skills essential for sustainability. Specifically, the study explores the availability and functionality of digital facilities, how effectively lecturers use these tools in instruction, and the extent to which their use has impacted students' performance and digital competence. Guided by three research questions and three hypotheses tested at a 0.05 level of significance, the study focuses on identifying available digital tools, evaluating student performance when exposed to digital strategies compared to conventional methods, and assessing students' digital literacy in contributing to sustainable development. The significance of this study lies in its potential to improve the learning and retention of science concepts among students while enhancing their attitude toward science through engaging and innovative instructional methods. Since science and technology play vital roles in sustainable development by addressing global issues such as climate change, economic instability, resource management, and health crises, integrating digital strategies into science education becomes crucial. Technology not only facilitates access to education but also promotes self-paced, interactive, and personalized learning experiences. Furthermore, digital literacy enables students to acquire employable skills, opening pathways to youth empowerment, employment, innovation, and national development. By bridging the gap between education and the demands of the modern workforce, the use of digital strategies in science education can enhance human capacity development and prevent setbacks in Nigeria's economic and social well-being.

Availability of Digital Infrastructure for Teaching and Learning for Sustainable Development

Eze & Aja in Owolabi, Oni, Mbanefo (2023) in their study found that on functionality, ICT devices were not available and most of the devices were not in good working condition in schools while other researches reveal that where they were available, they were not adequate. Nwosu, (2024) states that it was worthy of note that availability of ICT facilities deals with the extent to which ICT facilities are present or within reach. Despite the giant strides made to provide schools with ICT facilities, it is common knowledge that such facilities are not readily available.

Building students' capacity especially through digital strategies requires the provision of necessary resource materials to learn effectively. Quality delivery of instruction for sustainable development requires that modern infrastructure be available to meet the 21st century standard. Even though a lot of improvement have been made by some State governments to upgrade

these infrastructures during the lockdown, some of the public owned institutions still lag behind in digital infrastructures, laboratories, libraries, ICTs and power supplies. Building students' skills entails that stakeholders in education have to provide the necessary resource materials they require to learn effectively. It is not surprising that the prevailing learning condition of our educational institutions has a gap in educational policy and actual practice in Nigerian educational system. Owoeye & Oso (2024), observed that telegram, WhatsApp, Learning Management System and Zoom were the most prominent e-learning used during the lockdown of 2020. Students were also found to use smart phones frequently and e-learning tools enhanced lecturers and students' collaborations.

21st century Pedagogical Reawakening for Sustainable Development

Sustainable development is a way of understanding the world and methods of solving global issues. It is meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This involves job creation, increase productivity, encouraging innovations and ensuring that almost all persons have access to decent work and gainful employment, quality education and healthcare among others. A paradigm shift in teaching and learning brought about by COVID 19 Pandemic of 2019, led to building students' skill acquisition needs through the use of digital strategies approach. Jimola, & Ofodu, (2021), opined that the seismic change caused by the lockdown gave rise to the use of digital media and has showcased the essence of organizing educational activities to a large audience. Leveraging digital platforms like google classroom for real time and asynchronous learning helps learners assimilate better. Collaborating learning also allows students and teachers to interact freely and work together irrespective of the location. Smart classrooms were introduced. Smart classrooms are innovation in education that utilizes advanced technology to enhance students learning outcomes. Smart classrooms incorporate various elements like technology integration, internet connectivity, adaptive learning technologies and flexible learning spaces among others. Zoom for instance, has become popular in virtual classrooms. This invariably assisted in contributing to the development of creativity to improve students' and lecturers' awareness of key competencies needed for sustainable development.

Research has shown that a large number of lecturers are unskilled in incorporating technologies into teaching and learning. Lecturers have to adopt novel assessment techniques, provide participatory remote learning environment and design suitable e-resources that suit the new situation in the learning environment Ms Excel, PowerPoint, PDF reader; drawing apps help students in Science to experiment without physical waste of materials. ICT-literate students are observed to master content faster, better problem-solvers, more self-directed and assume greater control over learning. These assertions may be considered true, because learners are able to gain knowledge, have more comprehension and perform some analysis, synthesis and evaluate of content. Lecturers and students can draw, write, analyse and illustrate on the whiteboard, broadcast notes by sharing the screen, send audio and video recorded lecture lessons, do assignment and upload lecture notes. In Zoom virtual classroom, distortion or classroom disorder can be minimized. Lecturers can monitor their students' engagement, progress and ensure that they participate at the same time. Zoom is characterized by one-on-

one meetings, group video conferences, HD video and audio, scheduling, transcription features, security, screen sharing, camera, speaker, raising of hand, virtual background, chat-box, recording, and break-out rooms. Some past studies investigated the use of Zoom as a teaching/learning tool. These studies affirm that Zoom application is an effective educational platform which facilitates distance learning and enables discussion like in a real classroom.

Relationship between Learning Science Through Digital Strategies and Sustainable Development

Sustainable development requires citizens who are scientifically literate, innovative, and capable of addressing environmental, technological, and social challenges. According to the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG 4), Quality Education, digital technologies are critical to inclusive, equitable and quality education (UNESCO, 2019). Attention is paid to the use of digital learning tools that modify students learning styles during the lockdown and diverse digital tools that suit different learning styles. The combination of digital content and technology were used to enhance science students learning styles. Science has a prominent role to play in national development, manpower development and sustainability. The current innovation in teaching and learning of science has prompted lecturers to embark on the use of digital strategies and technological facilities to enhance productivity and creativity. Sustainable development is the development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of the future generations to meet their needs. The goal of sustainable development can be achieved with the presence of high workforce.

Digital Strategies, Digital literacy and Sustainable Development in Ekiti State University

Digital strategies refer to the planned integration of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) like e-learning platforms, virtual labs, simulations, mobile learning, and online collaborative tools into the instructional process to enhance teaching and learning outcomes. Digital strategies is a viable solution to improving learning outcomes, promoting learner-centred pedagogical approaches and creating agile education system. Digital literacy ensures that every learner has requisite digital skills and knowledge to cope in the 21st century classroom. Digital literacy cannot be obtained and used in isolation. There has to be technology infrastructure that will provide access to reliable and appropriate technology, online resources, digital content and software. The presence of these facilities will facilitate active learning that incorporates digital tools which can promote active engagement and collaboration. These ingredients are essential for skills development and building education systems that enhance the achievement of sustainable development. The COVID 19 pandemic led to the taking up of remote modality to ensure continuous learning and mitigate the effects of the stay at home. Ekiti State University swung into action to deploy options to support remote learning using different strategies. There were designed packages of materials like modules to support the development of both teachers and students' digital pedagogical competences. The effective use of these packages depends to a large extent on the digital literacy of both the teachers and the students. A researcher once remarked that some students do not know how to save a picture they find on the internet this shows that they lack digital literacy and skill.

Benefits of Teaching Science with Digital Strategies

Effective teaching of Science with digital strategies can significantly contribute to sustainable development. They equip individuals with the knowledge, skills and attitudes necessary to address global challenges and make good decisions for a sustainable future. Otoo-Arthur, Kabutey, Amoah, (2021) opine that the integration of e-learning in higher education has brought flexibility to teaching and learning, making teaching learner-centred. Effective teaching of science can significantly contribute to sustainable development, it equips individuals with the knowledge, skills, attitudes necessary to address global challenges and make good decisions for a sustainable future. Effective teaching of science fosters critical thinking, problem-solving, collaborative decision-making, enabling individuals to understand and address issues like climate change and resource management among others. Effective teaching of science plays a vital role in understanding complex problems like providing a foundation for understanding the origins, characteristics, consequences of global issues like climate change, biodiversity and resource depletion. It helps individuals grasp the interconnectedness of these problems and the complex chains of cause and effect. Sarker, Cao, Alam & Li. (2019) believe digital learning environment removes the barrier of time and location to learn and access to digital resources. Ode & Omeka (2019) carried out a study on the influence of ICT on academic performance of Science and Mathematics Education Students of Benue State University, Makurdi. The findings showed that integration of technology into teaching and learning had significant positive effect on students' academic performance hence their recommendation that ICT should be incorporated into teaching and learning and students should embrace the use of ICT in learning. They also discovered that technology enhanced learning and can foster a more engaging and active learning environment resulting in knowledge retention. It also helps students access array of learning materials like digital textbooks, and educational websites.

Effective teaching of science helps in developing problem-solving skills such as critical thinking and problem-solving which are essential ingredients for proffering solutions to sustainable development challenges. It equips individuals with the tools to design, evaluate and implement strategies for addressing environmental and social issues. Effective teaching of science promotes innovation and technological advancements that are crucial for developing sustainable solutions for renewable energy, efficient resource management and sustainable agriculture. It also empowers citizens to participate in decision-making processes related to sustainable development. Science teaching supports the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in achieving many of the SDGs that are related to quality education, climate action, sustainable communities, and production. Effective teaching of science contributes to scientific literacy and promotes sustainable practices not only by imparting scientific knowledge but also cultivating by a mindset and skillset that will enable individuals to become active and responsible citizens who can contribute to a more sustainable future.

Challenges of the Use of Digital Strategies in Teaching and Learning

The use of digital strategies is not without some challenges which include digital divide, internet connectivity, technical skills, need for training both educators and students, digital

literacy, limited infrastructure, limited human resources and pedagogical shift, that is, adapting teaching methods to digital environments.

METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted for this study was a mixed method involving quasi-experimental and descriptive survey using questionnaire. The experimental design was pre-test, post-test and quasi-experimental. The experimental group was treated with digital strategies package while the control group was taught with the conventional method. The pre-test was used to establish the students' entry characteristics before the commencement of the treatment to determine the efficacy of the package.

Instrumentation and Procedure

In the experimental procedure, the design is schematically represented below:

E O1 x1 O2-----this is the experimental group

C- O3 c O4-----this is the control group

E----- digital strategies package

C-----conventional method

O1, O3-----pre-test in E and C

O2, O4-----post-test in E and C

X1-----Experimental treatment (digital strategies package)

C-----conventional method used for the control group

The experimental and the control groups were given some questions in Biology, Chemistry and Physics to attempt as Pre-test to ascertain their level of knowledge of the courses. Thereafter, treatment was given and later both the experimental and the control groups were once again tested. This was the Post-test which determined the effectiveness of the package used in instruction. The sample consisted of 300 science students from Faculty of Science, Ekiti State University, Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria. All the students offering science were involved in both experimental and control groups. Two research instruments were used to collect data. One for experimental and Control. Questionnaire titled 'Effective use of Digital Strategies through Learning of Science for Sustainable Development in Ekiti State University was distributed to them to elicit necessary information from the students.

Experimental Procedure

The research procedure was in three stages. The pre-test, treatment and post-treatment stages.

Stage 1. The pre-test involved the gathering of students together and administering the questions before teaching them.

Stage 2. The treatment stage

This stage involves the treatment of the experimental group with digital strategies package. The treatment lasted for four weeks. The other research instrument was closed-ended questionnaire employed for data collection using google form. The questionnaire was made up of three parts. Part one centres on available digital facilities used for e-learning; Part two: investigates the accessibility and functionality of the digital facilities available for learning science. Part three: focuses on the digital strategies used for teaching and learning Science. Two research questions measure the available, not available, accessible not accessible, functional and not functional, a four-point-Likert-type scale (Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Strongly Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD). To ascertain the face and content validity of the instrument, experts in the fields of Information Technology and Test, Measurement and Evaluation were given the copies of the questionnaire; after a thorough scrutiny, the validity of the instrument was established. Data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using mean, standard deviation while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1 shows the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Pre-test stage It shows that science students exposed to digital strategies approach had mean score of 43.85 while those in the conventional group was 45.65 prior to treatment. The difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching was 1.80, indicating little disparity between their means. This implies that the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Pre-test stage is low.

Table 1: Mean performance scores of science students before treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Experimental	150	43.85	12.98	1.80
Conventional	150	45.65	16.24	
Total	300	44.75	14.70	

Table 2 presents the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Post-test stage It shows that science students exposed to digital strategies approach had higher mean score of 74.27 than those in the conventional group (mean = 45.65) after the treatment.

The difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at post-stage was 26.58, indicating a wide disparity between their mean scores. This implies that the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Post-test stage is high.

Table 2: Mean performance scores of science students after treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Mean Difference
Experimental	150	74.27	20.50	26.58
Conventional	150	47.69	14.11	
Total	300	60.98	22.04	

Table 2 shows that science students exposed to digital strategies approach had higher mean score of 74.27 than those in the conventional group (mean = 45.65) after the treatment. The difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at post-stage was 26.58, indicating a wide disparity between their mean scores. This implies that the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Post-test stage is high.

Question 3: How digital literate are the science students to contribute to sustainable development in Ekiti state university?

Table 3: Contribution of science students' digital literacy to sustainable development in Ekiti state university

S/N	Items	Very Effective	Effective	Never Effective	Mean
1	I can connect with my colleagues globally through zoom and Google Meet	121 (40.3)	167 (55.7)	12 (4.0)	2.36
2	I can make use of screen sharing when in a meeting with my lecturer	66 (22.0)	171 (57.0)	63 (21.0)	2.01
3	I can make use of virtual whiteboard during lectures	70 (23.3)	208 (69.3)	22 (7.3)	2.16
4	I can download and upload information/ online resources from internet.	79 (26.3)	197 (65.7)	24 (8.0)	2.18
5	I can source and share online information with lecturers and friends	63 (21.0)	199 (66.3)	38 (12.7)	2.08
6	Using digital strategies help me transfer knowledge and skills to real life problems	66 (22.0)	188 (62.7)	46 (15.3)	2.07
7	Digital tools help me develop critical and problem-solving skills using educational software and App	127 (42.3)	129 (43.0)	44 (13.7)	2.28
Criterion mean = 2.00, Percentage responses are enclosed in parentheses					

Table 3 presents the contribution of science students' digital literacy to sustainable development in Ekiti state university. Using a criterion mean score of 2.00 for the rating scale, all the items had mean scores above the cut-off point. This implies that science students who are digitally literate contribute to sustainable development in Ekiti State University.

Testing of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance.

Table 4: t-test of pre-test mean scores of science students' academic performance by treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P
Experimental	150	43.85	12.98	298	1.060	0.290
Control	150	45.65	16.24			

p>0.05

The result on Table 4 shows that science students exposed to digital strategies approach had slightly lower mean score (43.85) than their counterparts in the conventional group (45.65). The result further shows that computed t-value (1.060) with degree of freedom 298 was not statistically significant at p>0.05 level of significance for the groups. The null hypothesis was not rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance.

Table 5: t-test of post-test mean scores of science students' academic performance by treatment Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t	P
Experimental	150	74.27	20.50	298	13.085*	0.000
Control	150	47.69	14.11			

***p<0.05**

Table 5 depicts that science students exposed to digital strategies approach had higher mean score (74.27) than their counterparts in the conventional group (47.69). The result further indicates that computed t-value (13.085) with degree of freedom 298 was statistically significant at p<0.05 level of significance for the groups. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is a significant difference in the post-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance.

Hypothesis 3: There is no significant relationship between availability of digital facilities and students' academic performance in science.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation of availability of digital facilities and students' academic performance in science

Variable	N	Mean	SD	r	P
Availability of digital facilities	300	15.13	1.13	0.378*	0.000
Students' academic performance in science	300	60.98	22.04		

***p<0.05**

Table 6 shows that the computed r-value (0.378) is significant at p<0.05 level of significance. The null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between availability of digital facilities and students' academic performance in science. The correlation between availability of digital facilities and students' academic performance in science is moderate and statistically significant in a positive direction. The positive or direct correlation

implies that increase in availability of digital facilities will lead to corresponding increase in students' academic performance in science and vice-versa.

DISCUSSION

The study showed that the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Pre-test stage was low. This implies that the level of science students' performance prior to the treatment was very low. That their mean scores are very close to one another showed that these groups are homogenous. The study showed that the difference in mean performance scores of science students exposed to digital strategies approach and those taught with conventional method of teaching at Post-test stage was high. The observed difference could be attributed to the effects of treatment administered on the subjects, which showed that, the treatment was effective. It revealed that science students were highly digital literate to contribute to sustainable development in Ekiti State University. The finding agrees with the submission of Oloyede et al. (2021); Benmansour (2022). Their studies reiterate the suitability of digital strategies which included Zoom and Google Meet for future learning in the 21st century. The study revealed that there was no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance. This implies that the mean scores of science students in experimental and control group prior treatment was close. The reason for no significance was attributed to the constant use of traditional method of teaching with which they are all familiar.

The finding equally showed that there was a significant difference in the post-test mean scores of the experimental and control groups among science students' academic performance. The study further showed that there was significant relationship between availability of digital facilities and students' academic performance in science. The finding is consistent with that of Jimola, F. E. & Ofodu, G. O. (2021), and Owoeye & Oso (2024), that application of multimedia technology can help students learn vividly, clearly and realistically in the classroom, thereby improving their academic performance. It was concluded from the findings of this study that increase in availability of digital facilities led to corresponding increase in students' academic performance in science and vice versa. The academic performance of the science students was a testament to the efficacy of the package judging from their initial pre-test performance that was before the treatment, The study also revealed that science students were highly digital literate to contribute to sustainable development in Ekiti State University. Little wonder that Ekiti State University is rated the best among the State-owned Universities and the 12th among the Federal and State universities in Nigeria. The products of the University are also doing great in all their fields of endeavour as reported recently in one of the National dailies. The results presented an encouraging possibility that reimagining teaching and learning can be done and enriched in today's world of work thereby contribution to sustainable national development. Based on the findings, it was recommended that more digital facilities should be put in place to go round the students' ease of use instead of taking turns on the queue and sharing equipment. Lecturers should be sponsored and engaged in constant training through workshops and seminars to update them in the use of digital strategies.

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